

Exploiting Human Intrinsic Kinematic Null Space to Control Extra Degrees of Freedom

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Abstract—Developing effective control strategies for super-numerary robotic limbs (SRLs) is an open challenge. A key aspect that remains insufficiently addressed is the formulation of successful and intuitive policies that do not hinder the functionality of a person's natural limbs. This work introduces an innovative strategy based on the exploitation of the redundancy of the human kinematic chain. The procedure encompasses a real-time analysis of body motion and a subsequent computation of the control signal for SRLs based on the body redundancy for single-arm tasks. This concept is summarized in the definition of the Intrinsic Kinematic Null Space (IKNS).

We studied the users' capability of exploiting the proposed method both in virtual and real environments. Obtained results demonstrated that the exploitation of the IKNS allows to perform complex tasks involving both biological and artificial limbs, and that practice improves the ability to accurately manage the coordination of human and supernumerary artificial limbs.

I. INTRODUCTION

Supernumerary robotic limbs (SRLs) offer the possibility to compensate or augment human capabilities in terms of perception and manipulation abilities [1], allowing individuals to perform complex sensorimotor tasks by coordinating biological and artificial limbs. Differently from prostheses and exoskeletons, SRLs represent additional degrees of freedom (DoFs) that need to be controlled independently from and simultaneously with biological limbs.

The cutting-edge component to implement the idea of augmentation is the design of wearable sensorimotor interfaces. From a broad perspective, these interfaces are meant for establishing a bidirectional connection between the human sensorimotor system and the robot's system of actuators and sensors. Through this connection, reciprocal awareness, trustworthiness, and mutual understanding are intended to be achieved, enhancing the overall integration between the user and the SRLs. For instance, as visually summarized in Fig. 1, by capturing signals from human body motion the sensorimotor interfaces can leverage the redundancy of

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Fig. 1: An impaired subject exploiting the redundancy of the arm involved in the task to control the robotic extra-limb, while simultaneously holding the glass.

the human sensorimotor system to map commands for the robot limbs. To take a significant stride towards realizing this ambitious scenario, our work presents a novel methodology to extract a signal from the human kinematic redundancy for enabling the simultaneous control of natural and artificial limbs during task execution.

II. INTRINSIC KINEMATIC NULL SPACE

Adapting the concept of robotic kinematic null space to the human body is not a straightforward operation: differently from a serial robotic manipulator, humans have more than one end-effector (e.g., hands and feet) and can perform multiple tasks at the same time. Thus, for identifying the exploitable degrees of freedom, it is necessary to specify which is the considered end-effector and, consequently, the task we refer to. From this perspective, considering the kinematic space of the whole body, we can make a distinction between two types of null space:

- i) Extrinsic Kinematic Null Space (EKNS);
- ii) Intrinsic Kinematic Null Space (IKNS).

Considering a task to be accomplished, joints which are not involved in such a task belong to the first category, whereas the latter refers only to joints directly employed in the task. For instance, grabbing a box with two hands involves joints of shoulders, upper arms, forearms, and wrists. Motions of all the other joints (e.g., knees and ankles) are in the Explicit Kinematic Null Space. On the contrary, the motion of the

Fig. 2: The procedure to identify and exploit the IKNS for controlling an extra DoF.

joints of shoulders, upper arms, forearms, and wrists which does not generate velocities of the hand belongs to the Intrinsic Kinematic Null Space.

Bearing in mind the control of SRLs, taking advantage of movements in the Intrinsic Kinematic Null Space lets the user move a device using body parts already involved in the task, without compromising the use of free limbs which instead may be involved in further parallel tasks. In this work we focused our attention on exploiting motions in the IKNS in the specific use case of controlling a SRL while performing single-arm tasks, since we identified them as critical for impaired people and the most paradigmatic for presenting this innovative approach. To identify the IKNS in a simple single-arm task, the procedure visually reported in Fig. 2 was adopted. Interested reader may refer to [2] for further details and a more accurate description.

III. EXPERIMENTAL VALIDATION

Four experiments were conducted both in virtual and real environments to address four research questions. Overall, 40 subjects participated in the experimental campaign. All the experiments were performed in a room equipped with a Vicon system to online reconstruct the body posture by means of Vicon Nexus 3.10 Software.

Experiment 1: *Is it possible to use the IKNS to control an extra degree of freedom to execute dual tasks?*

Participants were asked to seat and move their upper limb to control the position and the radius of a virtual sphere. The goal of the experiment was to overlap two spheres: one controlled by the user, and one considered the target. Two different conditions were tested. While in both conditions the radius was changed by exploiting the IKNS, in the first condition the position of the target sphere was fixed while in the second condition the user had also to change the position of the target sphere by moving the hand. Results revealed that using the IKNS to control an additional degree of freedom in a dual task did not affect the performance of the primary task.

Experiment 2: *How is the user control ability affected by practice considering the difficulty of the task?*

In this experiment, each user was asked to use their hand position to directly control the position of a cursor and match a target placed in one of the nine spatial positions around the rest position, which was a sphere located in front of them. Targets were spherical or prolate spheroids. Users were asked to control simultaneously cursor position and orientation around the axis passing through the equatorial radius of the

spheroid and normal to the targets plane, exploiting the IKNS-based control signal to adjust the orientation. Each participant repeated 72 trials, in which they were asked to match 9 targets with different difficulties. Control strategy performance were evaluated considering four metrics: *i)* reaching success rate, computed as the percentage of reached targets, *ii)* holding success rate, computed as the percentage of targets held for at least 1 second, *iii)* holding time, computed as the maximum time the cursor held the target matched within 10 seconds, and *iv)* angular error, computed as the difference between cursor and target orientation when the cursor position was within the spatial tolerance. An information theory-based approach based on [3] was adopted to devise a model of the participant motor behaviour.

Outcomes indicate not only that practice positively influences users' control ability, but also that the target specific difficulty needs to be taken into account. Furthermore, to support the previous findings, two additional metrics were investigated: angular and spatial velocities of the cursor. The two velocities and the related peaks were analysed to assess whether different participants used different strategies for reaching and matching the targets. Multiple statistical test were conducted to determine whether there was a statistically significant difference between the peaks of linear and angular velocities while accomplishing the task.

Results suggested that participants maintained unaltered their strategy throughout the experiment, i.e. they adjusted the cursor orientation only when the centre of the spheroids were almost aligned.

Experiment 3: *Is the IKNS-based control easy to learn for controlling a wearable extra-finger to accomplish common activities of daily living requiring simultaneous tasks?*

To answer this question, users were asked to perform a repetitive pick-and- place task. They wore a robotic extra-finger on the right forearm, mimicking a post-stroke hemiparesis, and controlled the position of the opening/closing mechanism with the same arm using the IKNS. Results show that participants rapidly learned how to use the system, and gained confidence in picking and releasing the cube.

The slope of the learning curve demonstrates that with few trials users are able to take advantage of the IKNS-based control for accomplishing dual tasks with a wearable robotic extra-finger.

Experiment 4: *How does user performance in accomplishing common activities of daily living that involve simultaneous tasks differ when using the IKNS-based control compared to an EKNS-based control?*

Participants were instructed to use a grounded supernumerary robotic arm (Kinova Mico2) to pour a glass of water. Similarly to the previous experiment, the participants were given two tasks to complete simultaneously: holding the glass under the bottle, and precisely controlling the robot to pour exactly 30 grams of water. Subjects were asked to repeat the task under two experimental conditions, that is controlling the velocity of the joint using once the IKNS-based control signal extracted from the same arm holding the glass, and once using the EKNS-based control signal extracted from the dorsiflexion of their right foot.

Statistical analysis of the results demonstrated that the differences in water pouring accuracy between the IKNS and EKNS methods were not statistically significant. However, it is worth noting that using the IKNS to control the SRL required more time to complete the pouring task.

IV. CONCLUSION

We developed a novel approach to control extra DoFs exploiting the human body kinematic redundancy and demonstrated the feasibility in controlling SRLs. Such an approach can be applied to more sophisticated assistive or augmentative robotic devices (as extra limbs/arm wearable or not) in everyday life situations, for both healthy and impaired people. The proposed method may be used, for instance, by impaired (including several impaired) patients to compensate for their disability using the same limb (the healthy one) both to accomplish a task and for controlling a robot in a cooperative way. In future studies we will evaluate the cognitive load needed for using such approach that might be too high for a frail person.

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